

Signal Criterion for use of Nonlinear Encoding of Communications Signals

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Abstract – This paper attempts to provide criteria that can be applied to signals to determine if a nonlinear encoding technique provides an improved signal characterization.

Keywords: Analog to Digital Conversion, Non-Linear Encoding, Mixed signals, Sampling

1 Introduction

Traditional A/D conversion has used linear encoding techniques due to the monolithic nature of most A/D converters and uncertainty of the signal that will be converted. If the user either has a priori knowledge of the signal or can develop knowledge of the signal environment then improved resolution may be achieved by use of a nonlinear encoder. This paper will present the criteria that need to be satisfied in order to use this nonlinear encoding.

2 Nonlinear encoding A/Ds

2.1 Previous work

Previous investigators in the field have heavily concentrated on low frequency, voice transmission with an emphasis on the compression and decompression of voice signals for telephone transmission. [1] [2]. The American standard for compressive A/D, μ Law, is able to compress a 13 bit resolution into an 8 bit encoding with no audible distortion. This is due to the sensitivity of human hearing rather than the accuracy of the conversion.

Non-linear A/Ds have also been used in low frequency Sonar applications where resolution needs to be as high as possible but conversion rate is not an issue. [3][4]

In a previous paper [5] a nonlinear Flash A/D architecture was discussed that took advantage of the distribution of samples of a full range sine wave. The architecture proposed a reduction of 25% of the comparators which will reduce the power consumption, size and thermal considerations at the cost a small increase in least significant bit errors. This was achieved by removing half of the comparators from the middle of the voltage range of the A/D and reducing the component count of the flash architecture from 2^n to $(2^n - 2^{n-2})$. This reduction was made possible by the knowledge of the sample distribution across the voltage input range of

the A/D and noted that, for a sine wave that occupied the full voltage range, the majority of the A/D samples occur between encodings 0 to 64 and 192 to 256 for an eight bit A/D (see figure 1, 2).

Figure 1 A full range Sine wave

The values from figure 1 shows the samples from zero to $\pi/6$ and from $5\pi/6$ to π in the voltage range between 1V and 1.5V this compares to the other $2/3$ s of π in the range from 1.5V and 2V. There is a similar amount of time from the zones between 0.5V and 1V and the voltage zone between 0V and 0.5V. A histogram of these samples is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 A histogram by voltage range of fig 1

2.2 A More Realistic Environment

A more realistic environment for the operation of an A/D will include not only the intended signal but also unintended signals and noise. The full signal found at the input to the A/D is:

$$d = n_o + S_j + \sum_{i=0}^k S_i$$

where

Total signal (d) = Noise (n_o) + expected signal (S_j) + sum of other signals present ($\sum_{i=0}^k S_i$)

If d is amplified or attenuated such that $|d| = \text{Dynamic range of the A/D (d = 1)}$ and I further define y as a sample of d . Because d is an analog value the difference between d and y is the quantization error. For a linear encoder of n bits resolution this quantization error of d is uniformly distributed between adjacent values of y such that:

$$\text{Error}(y) \sim \text{UNI} \left[\theta_1 = 0, \theta_2 = \frac{\text{range}}{2^n} \right]; 0 \leq d \leq \text{range}$$

θ indicates the range of errors (rounding errors) that occur as a result of digitization. This error function does not account for clock errors which will be ignored for this paper.

2.3 Nonlinear encoding

In the referenced earlier paper we described a nonlinear encoder that used a reduced number of components to implement a flash architecture.

A similar nonlinear architecture could be achieved by manipulating the voltage references to a series of linear A/Ds. An example of how this could be practically achieved is to use three A/Ds that have the same resolution. Use one each for the top and bottom forth of the voltage range and the third for the middle.

Regardless of implementation the resulting encoder will encode the signal with eight bit resolution on the outer half of the range and seven bit in the middle with the transfer function shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Non-Linear voltage transfer

2.4 Nonlinear quantization error

The A/D conversion errors from this type of nonlinear process will be:

$$\text{Error}(z) \begin{cases} \sim \text{UNI} \left[\theta_1 = 0, \theta_2 = \frac{d}{2^{n+1}} \right]; 0 \leq y < \frac{d}{4} \text{ or} \\ \frac{3}{4}d < y \leq d \\ \sim \text{UNI} \left[\theta_1 = 0, \theta_2 = \frac{d}{2^{n-1}} \right]; \frac{d}{4} \leq y \leq \frac{3d}{4} \end{cases}$$

Where $d \approx \text{range}$

The benefit from using the non-linear encoding will be realized when the sum of the quantization errors of z (the non-linear quantization) is less than the sum of the quantization errors of y (the linear quantization), or:

$$\Sigma \text{Error}(z) < \Sigma \text{Error}(y)$$

In order to meet this criterion the signal of interest must have a distribution of samples where more than half of the samples lie in the outer half of the voltage range. The criterion will be met if the expected signal S_j forms at least .7071 of the total amplitude of the input signal d . In this case S_j will be present in the outer half of the conversion range from $\pi/4 < y < 3\pi/4$ and $5\pi/4 < y < 7\pi/4$ or half the cycle. This represents a signal to noise ratio at the input to the A/D converter of

$$\text{SNR} = 20 \log(A(S_j)/A(n_o + S_i))$$

In the worst case

$$\text{SNR} = 20 \log(.7071/.2929) = +7.65 \text{ dB}$$

This SNR can be easily achieved for many types of modulation by filtering the input signal before amplification and A/D conversion.

3 Future Directions

As noted earlier in the paper, the user may achieve a better representation of the signal by using a nonlinear encoding if it meets this specific criterion. Unfortunately, the user often does not know whether the criteria have been met before digitizing starts. A future implementation could start digitizing using a linear encoder and then adapt to the environment by modifying the conditioning gain to the A/D and by changing the reference voltages to the A/Ds to change the transfer function of the A/D process and achieve the best resolution.

4 Conclusions

The author of this paper would like to acknowledge Dr. Charles Cerny, Dr. Braham Himed and Dr. Erik Blasch for their constructive insights during technical discussions that have shaped this topic area.

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